

Assessing IDEA Diagrams for Supporting Analysis of Capabilities and Issues in Technical Debt Management

Complementary Material

This document presents the auxiliary material related to the paper published in PROFES 2023. This paper aims to empirically assess the IDEA diagrams with respect to their ease of use, usefulness, potential future use, and support for technical debt management.

Fig. 1. Perceived usefulness for IDEA Diagram for TD Prevention.

Fig. 2. Perceived usefulness for IDEA Diagram for TD Monitoring.

Fig. 3. Perceived usefulness for IDEA Diagram for TD Repayment.

Fig. 4. The IDEA diagram for design debt repayment.

Table 1. TAM evaluation form.

No.	Question (Q) Description	Options
Q1	What is your name?	Open
Q2	What is your email address?	Open
Q3	Regarding the usefulness of using diagrams to support the identification of practices and PARs associated with technical debt prevention activities, choose the option that best represents your point of view: a. Using the proposed diagrams, I would be able to identify practices for TD prevention more quickly. (Quick) b. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my performance in identifying practices for TD prevention . (Activity Performance) c. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my effectiveness in identifying practices for TD prevention . (Effectiveness) d. Using the proposed diagrams would make easy to identify practices for TD prevention . (Makes activity easier) e. Using the proposed diagrams, I would be able to identify PARs related to TD non-prevention more quickly. (Quick) f. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my performance in identifying PARs related to TD non-prevention . (Activity Performance) g. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my effectiveness in identifying PARs related to TD non-prevention . (Effectiveness) h. Using the proposed diagrams would make easy to identify PARs related to TD non-prevention . (Makes activity easier)	Strongly agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly disagree
Q4	Regarding the usefulness of using diagrams to support the identification of practices and PARs associated with technical debt monitoring activities, choose the option that best represents your point of view: a. Using the proposed diagrams, I would be able to identify practices for TD monitoring more quickly. (Quick) b. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my performance in identifying practices for TD monitoring . (Activity Performance) c. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my effectiveness in identifying practices for TD monitoring . (Effectiveness) d. Using the proposed diagrams would make easy to identify practices for TD monitoring . (Makes activity easier) e. Using the proposed diagrams, I would be able to identify PARs related to TD non-monitoring more quickly. (Quick) f. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my performance in identifying PARs related to TD non-monitoring . (Activity Performance) g. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my effectiveness in identifying PARs related to TD non-monitoring . (Effectiveness) h. Using the proposed diagrams would make easy to identify PARs related to TD non-monitoring . (Makes activity easier)	Strongly agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly disagree
Q5	Regarding the usefulness of using diagrams to support the identification of practices and PARs associated with technical debt repayment activities, choose the option that best represents your point of view: a. Using the proposed diagrams, I would be able to identify practices for TD repayment more quickly. (Quick)	Strongly agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly disagree

	b. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my performance in identifying practices for TD repayment . (Activity Performance)	
	c. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my effectiveness in identifying practices for TD repayment . (Effectiveness)	
	d. Using the proposed diagrams would make easy to identify practices for TD repayment . (Makes activity easier)	
	e. Using the proposed diagrams, I would be able to identify PARs related to TD non- repayment more quickly. (Quick)	
	f. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my performance in identifying PARs related to TD non- repayment . (Activity Performance)	
	g. Using the proposed diagrams, I would improve my effectiveness in identifying PARs related to TD non- repayment . (Effectiveness)	
	h. Using the proposed diagrams would make easy to identify PARs related to TD non- repayment . (Makes activity easier)	
Q6	Regarding the usefulness of using diagrams to support the identification of practices and PARs associated with technical debt prevention, monitoring, and repayment activities, choose the option that best represents your point of view:	Strongly agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly disagree
	a. Using the proposed diagrams, I would increase my productivity.	
	b. I believe that the proposed diagrams would be useful to support technical debt management.	
Q7	Regarding the ease of use of the diagrams to support the identification of practices and PARs associated with the activities of prevention, monitoring and payment of technical debt, choose the option that best represents your point of view:	Strongly agree Agree Neutral Disagree Strongly disagree
	a. Learning to operate the proposed diagrams would be easy for me. (Easy to learn)	
	b. My interaction with the proposed diagrams would be clear and understandable. (Clear and understandable)	
	c. I would find it easy to use the proposed diagrams to identify practices for TD prevention . (Controllable)	
	d. I would find it easy to use the proposed diagrams to identify PARs for TD non-prevention . (Controllable)	
	e. I would find it easy to use the proposed diagrams to identify practices for TD monitoring . (Controllable)	
	f. I would find it easy to use the proposed diagrams to identify PARs for TD non-monitoring . (Controllable)	
	g. I would find it easy to use the proposed diagrams to identify practices for TD repayment . (Controllable)	
	h. I would find it easy to use the proposed diagrams to identify PARs for TD non-repayment . (Controllable)	
	i. It would be easy to become skillful in using the proposed diagrams. (Skillful)	
	j. It would be easy to remember how to identify practices and PARs related to TD prevention, monitoring, and repayment using the proposed diagrams. (Remember)	
	k. I find the support easy to use. (Ease to use)	
Q8	Regarding a possible future use of the diagrams to support the identification of practices and PARs associated with the activities of prevention, monitoring and payment of technical debt, choose the option that best represents your point of view:	Strongly agree Agree Neutral Disagree

	a. Assuming the proposed diagrams would be available to manage technical debt, I would use them in the future.	Strongly disagree
	b. I would rather use the proposed diagrams than identify practices and PARs associated with prevention, monitoring and payment of technical debt in the usual way (without the support of the diagrams).	
Q9	According to your opinion, list the positive aspects of using diagrams:	Open
Q10	According to your opinion, list the negative aspects of using diagrams:	Open
Q11	If so, please indicate any suggestions for improving the diagrams used.	Closed
Q12	Did the use of the diagrams help you identify technical debt prevention, monitoring or payment practices that you would not have identified without their support?	Yes/No
Q13	Did the use of the diagrams help you identify PARs for non-prevention, non-monitoring, or non-payment of technical debt that you would not have identified without their support?	Yes/No

Table 2. Interview script.

Section	Question
Opening	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We present the consent form. • We present the concept of technical debt as defined by McConnell¹.
	Q1. Concerning your experience with TD management:
	a) Never heard of it.
	b) I have heard of it, but I have not been on projects where I recognized TD.
	c) I have been on projects where I recognized TD but the project did not explicitly manage it.
	d) I have been on projects where we attempted to actively manage TD.
	Q1.1. Have you or your project ever used any strategies for managing TD items?
	Q1.2. What are these strategies? Can you explain how you have used them?
	Q1.3. Have you or your project ever used any tools for managing TD items?
	Q1.4. What are these tools? Can you explain how you have used them?
Perception of IDEA diagrams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We present the IDEA diagrams, explaining their structure and use for supporting TD management.
	Q2. Would you think the IDEA diagrams easy to read and follow to support decisions about TD management? Why?
	Q3. Would the IDEA diagrams influence any of your decisions about how to manage TD items? Why?
	Q4. Would you think percentages are useful to guide the choice of practices and reasons? Why?
	Q5. Assuming the IDEA diagrams were available at your job, would you use them for supporting your TD management activities? Why?
	Q5.1. Do you think IDEA diagrams fit your reality?
	Q5.2. What adjustments do you suggest?
Closing	Q6. Is there anything else you would like to add?
	Please, fill the characterization questionnaire (See Table 3).

¹ The TD definition used in the interview is adapted from McConnell (2007)**: “Technical debt contextualizes the problem of outstanding software development tasks (for example, tests planned but not executed, pending code refactoring, pending documentation update, use of bad design practices, code that does not exhibit good coding practices) as a kind of debt that brings a short-term benefit to the project (normally in terms of higher productivity or shorter release time of software versions), that may have to be paid later in the development process with interest (for example, a poorly designed class tends to be more difficult and costly to maintain than if it had been implemented good object-oriented practices)”.
 ** Steve McConnell, 2007. Technical debt, 10x Software Development Blog. Construx Conversations. URL=<http://blogs.construx.com/blogs/stevemcc/archive/2007/11/01/technical-debt-2.aspx>.

Table 3. Characterization questionnaire.

No.	Question (Q) Description	Options
Q1	What is your name?	Open
Q2	What is the size of your company?	a) 1-10 employees b) 11-50 employees c) 51-250 employees d) 251-500 employees e) 501-1000 employees f) 1001-2000 employees g) More than 2000 employees
Q3	To which project role are you currently assigned?	a) Business analyst b) DBA/Data analyst c) Developer d) Process analyst e) Project leader / Project manager f) Requirements analyst g) Software architect h) Test manager/Tester i) Other
Q4	How do you rate your experience in this role?	a) Novice (Minimal or “textbook” knowledge without connecting it to practice) b) Beginner (Working knowledge of key aspects of practice) c) Competent (Good working and background knowledge of area of practice) d) Proficient (Depth of understanding of discipline and area of practice) e) Expert (Authoritative knowledge of discipline and deep tacit understanding across area of practice)
Q5	Which of the following most closely describes the development process model you follow on this project?	a) Agile (a lightweight process that promotes iterative development, close collaboration between the development team and business side, constant communication, and tightly-knit teams) b) Hybrid (is the combination of agile methods with other non-agile techniques. For example, a detailed requirements effort, followed by sprints of incremental delivery) c) Traditional (conventional document-driven software development methods that can be characterized as extensive planning, standardization of development stages, formalized communication, significant documentation and design up front)